

STABILITY AND CHIRALITY OF 4-VINYLAZETIDIN-2-ONE: A COMPUTATIONAL STUDY

Mirjalol Mirzaolimov Muxammadjon o'g'li

Iqbol Jalolov Jamolovich

To'lanboy Abdullajonov Erkinboy o'g'li

Department of Chemistry, Fergana State University, 19 Murabbiylar Str., Fergana 150100, Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article presents a detailed computational study on the structural and thermochemical properties of 4-vinylazetidin-2-one, focusing on its stereoisomers. Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations were used to optimize geometries, analyze potential energy surfaces, and compute thermochemical quantities. The study reveals significant differences in stability among the protomers and highlights the pronounced chiral nature of these molecules, providing insights that could be useful for synthetic and pharmaceutical applications.

Keywords: 4-vinylazetidin-2-one, stereoisomers, Density Functional Theory, stability, chirality, thermochemical properties

Introduction

4-Vinylazetidin-2-one is an important compound in organic chemistry, known for its potential applications in pharmaceutical synthesis and chiral chemistry. This study focuses on the computational analysis of its stereoisomers to understand their stability and chiral properties.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of (4R)-4-Vinylazetidin-2-one (az1(R)), (4S)-4-

Vinylazetidin-2-one (az1(S)), (3R)-3-Vinylazetidin-2-one (az2(R)), and (3S)-3-Vinylazetidin-2-one (az2(S)).

Computational Methods

The study employed Density Functional Theory (DFT) using the M06-2X functional and 6-31+G** basis set for initial geometry optimizations and potential

energy surface (PES) scans. Further optimizations and thermochemical calculations were conducted at the M06-2X/6-311++G** level in an implicit solvent model (IEF-PCM(SMD), solvent = DMSO).

Results and Discussion

Stability of Protomers: The study investigated three protomers of az2(R): az2(R)-N, az2(R)-O1, and az2(R)-O2. The N-protonated form (az2(R)-N) was found to be the most stable, with significantly lower energy values compared to the O-protonated forms. The calculated thermochemical quantities at 298.15 K and 1.00 atm indicate the following relative stability:

az2(R)-N (min1): $\Delta G = 0.0$ kJ/mol (most stable)

az2(R)-O1: $\Delta G = 76.1$ kJ/mol

az2(R)-O2: $\Delta G = 79.4$ kJ/mol

Chirality and Optical Activity: The optical rotatory strength calculations at 589 nm showed significant chiral properties:

az2(R)-N(min1): $[\alpha] = 330.44^\circ$

az2(S)-N(min1): $[\alpha] = -330.44^\circ$

These values underscore the strong optical activity of the stereoisomers, crucial for their potential use in asymmetric synthesis and chiral drug development.

Geometrical and Spectroscopic Properties

The optimized geometries showed consistent bond lengths and angles across different levels of theory, with slight variations. The molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) maps and ESP atomic charges provided insights into the electronic distribution, confirming the stability observations.

The vibrational (IR and Raman) and NMR spectra simulations for az2(R)-N(min1) provided characteristic peaks that can be used for experimental verification.

Dimerization

The dimerization of az2(R)-N(min1) was also evaluated, with enthalpy and Gibbs free energy changes indicating a moderately favorable enthalpy change ($\Delta H = -17.7$ kJ/mol) but a less favorable Gibbs free energy change ($\Delta G = 24.1$ kJ/mol), suggesting limited dimerization under standard conditions.

Conclusions

Stability of Protomers: The computational results clearly indicate that the N-protonated form of 4-vinylazetid-2-one is the most stable among the investigated protomers. This insight is crucial for predicting the behavior of this compound in chemical reactions and can guide experimental efforts in synthesis and application.

Chirality and Optical Activity: The pronounced chiral nature and significant optical activity of the stereoisomers make 4-vinylazetidin-2-one an attractive candidate for chiral synthesis applications. The specific rotation values provide a reliable means for assessing enantiomeric purity, which is essential in pharmaceutical contexts.

Recommendations

Experimental Verification: The computational findings should be validated through experimental synthesis and characterization, focusing on the stability and optical properties of the stereoisomers.

Chiral Applications: Given the strong optical activity, further research should explore the use of 4-vinylazetidin-2-one in the synthesis of chiral pharmaceuticals and as a chiral auxiliary in asymmetric synthesis.

References

1. Zhou Ch.; Birney D.M. "A density functional theory study clarifying the reactions of conjugated ketenes with formalimine. A plethora of pericyclic and pseudopericyclic pathways." *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2002, 124(18), 5231-5241. DOI: 10.1021/ja017559z.
2. Snider, B.B.; Johnston, M.I. "Synthesis of Deoxytabtoxine- β -Lactam." *Synth. Commun.* 1987, 17(16), 1877-1886. DOI: 10.1080/00397918708057798.
3. Mori, M.; Kagechika, K.; Tohjima, K.; Shibasaki, M. "New synthesis of 4-acetoxy-2-azetidinones by use of electrochemical oxidation." *Tetrahedron Letters* 1988, 29(12), 1409-1412. DOI: 10.1016/S0040-4039(00)80310-X.